

Research Article

Electrolytes and Lipid Profile Patterns Observed in Kidney Dysfunctional State Subjects on Haemodialysis

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Abstract

This study evaluated the electrolyte and lipid profiles of haemodialysed patients with kidney failure. A total of 150 subjects who consented provided the sample size. Venous blood sample was collected from the subjects and they were spun to obtain plasma having used Heparin as anticoagulant. Electrolyte profile sodium, potassium, chloride and bicarbonate were analyzed. The lipid profiles were demonstrated with cholesterol, triglyceride, high density lipoprotein cholesterol and low density lipoprotein cholesterol. All parameters were determined spectrophotometrically. Data of result from 3 tested groups Normal (Control), Pre-Dialysis and Post-dialysis were analyzed. We observed significant difference in the analytes for sodium, triglyceride, high density lipoprotein having used both descriptive and analysis of variance statistics along with Post Hoc Turkey HSD test via IBM SPSS version 27. The significance level was set at $P < 0.05$. For HDL, the mean \pm standard deviation was 1.63 ± 0.20 mmol/L for the control group, 0.48 ± 0.18 mmol/L for the test B group with $F = 8.75$ and P value < 0.01 . The mean \pm standard deviation for low-density lipoprotein for the control, Test A and B groups were 1.83 ± 0.82 mmol/L, 3.59 ± 1.34 mmol/L and 3.87 ± 1.35 mmol/L respectively with $F = 4.29$ and P value < 0.01 . It is concluded that stringent monitoring of electrolyte especially sodium and lipid profile evaluation will enhance management in Renal failure patients.

Key words: Electrolytes, Lipid, Profile, Kidney, Haemodialysis

Introduction

One of the procedures used to manage patients with kidney failure is Haemodialysis. The procedure involves purifying the blood externally after it has been extracted from a vessel and pass through a synthetic filter called a dialyzer. The role of the dialyzer is to purify the blood and then returned to the patients, playing the role of an artificial kidney.

Haemodialysis is often conducted for uremic patients [1]. Dialysis is known to alleviate most symptoms of renal failure although further pharmacological interventions are necessary in presence of complication such as hypertension and anaemia [2].

Renal failure refers to the kidney's inability to sustain excretory functions, which include electrolyte and volume management, excretion of nitrogenous waste, elimination of foreign molecules (including several medications), synthesis of several hormones such as erythropoietin and metabolism of low molecular weight protein such as insulin. Renal failure is classified into two categories [3]. Acute and Chronic. Acute Renal Failure (ARF) is characterized by a rapid drop in glomerular filtration rate lasting for hours or days but is typically reversible. Chronic Renal Failure (CRF) also known as Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) is characteristically defined by a concomitant and sustained deterioration in kidney function [4].

Electrolytes such as sodium, potassium, chloride, and bicarbonate play crucial role in maintenance of fluid balance, neuron function and muscle contraction. Imbalances in electrolytes like low sodium (hyponatremia), raised potassium (hyperkalemia), low chloride (hypochloremia) and elevated bicarbonate (metabolic acidosis) can have significant clinical effects

indicating renal failure .

In End State Kidney Disease (ESKD), the kidneys cannot effectively filter waste materials and excess fluid from the circulation which results in symptoms such as nausea exhaustion and weakness. During dialysis, waste materials and excess fluid are removed from the body by filtering it via a machine. In this research work, we determined the profiles of Electrolytes and lipids in Normal patients and those undergoing haemodialysis.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The cross-sectional design study was carried in Port Harcourt, Rivers State of Nigeria. Subjects for the study was made up of males and females between the age ranges of 30-80 years whose written consent were obtained. Ten (10) mls of venous blood was collected from the 150 subjects and dispensed into lithium heparine containers. The samples were spun and separated and the plasma was used for analysis.

Sodium was determined colorimetrically using the method based on reaction of sodium with a selective chromogen producing chromophore whose absorbance varies as the concentration of sodium in the test specimen.

Potassium was determined by the Thiocyanate-Hg colorimetric method while Bicarbonate was determined by Titration method based on back Titration of Bicarbonate with HCL in which excess HCL was titrated with sodium hydroxide using phenol red as indicator.

Triglycerides were determined colorimetrically after enzymatic hydrolysis with lipase. The indicator is a quinonemine formed from hydrogen perox-

ide, 4-aminophenazone and 4-chlorophenol under the catalytic influence of peroxidase measured at 520nm wavelength.

Total cholesterol and High density lipoprotein were determined colorimetrically using product of (spectrum). The estimation of Low density lipoprotein cholesterol was done through calculation of data obtained for Total Cholesterol, Triglyceride and high density lipoprotein according to the Fried Wald's Equation:

$$\text{LDL mmol/L} = \text{Total Cholesterol} - (\text{Triglyceride} + \text{HDL Chol}) / 22$$

RESULTS

Results obtained from the analysis of Electrolytes Sodium, Potassium, Chloride and Bicarbonates are shown in Table 1, while those of the lipid profiles cholesterol, Triglyceride, High Density lipoprotein, and Low density lipoprotein are shown in Table 2.

Table 1: Comparison of the Mean and Standard Deviation of Concentrations of electrolytes between study groups.

Parameter	Control n=50	Test A (Pre-dialysis) n=50	Test B (Post-dialysis) n=50	F Value	P Value	Remark
Sodium (mmol/L)	134.40±3.41	146.01±8.62	147.30±11.45	6.98	0.00	SS
Potassium (mmol/L)	4.321±0.924	5.46±2.96	5.83±2.10	0.184	0.84	NSS
Chloride (mmol/L)	106.89±6.77	108.04±7.60	109.12±6.06	0.27	0.77	NSS
Bicarbonate (mmol/L)	21.11±7.29	27.43±10.82	28.01±11.23	3.03	0.07	NSS

Values of P < 0.05 are considered statistically significant.

Table 2: Comparison of the Mean and Standard Deviation of Lipid Profile among the Study Subjects.

Groups	N	TC (mmol/L) Mean + SD	TG (mmol/L) Mean + SD	HDL (mmol/L) Mean + SD	LDL (mmol/L) Mean + SD
Control	50	4.16 ± 0.73	1.55 ± 0.66	4.63 ± 0.20	1.83 ± 0.82
Test A	50	5.59 ± 1.22	1.67 ± 0.41	0.48 ± 0.18	3.59 ± 1.34
Test B	50	4.86 ± 1.36	1.41 ± 0.31	0.34 ± 0.11	3.87 ± 1.35
F-Value		4.76	7.97	8.75	4.29
P-Value		0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
Remark		SS	SS	SS	SS
Post Hoc					
T ₁ V _s T ₂		NSS (0.15)	SS (<0.01)	SS (<0.01)	SS (<0.01)
T ₁ V _s T ₃		SS (0.01)	NSS (0.35)	SS (<0.01)	SS (<0.01)
T ₂ V _s T ₃		NSS (0.48)	SS (0.03)	SS (<0.01)	NSS (0.46)

P < 0.05 = Statistically significant

Key: T₁ = Control (Normal subjects without CKD), T₂ = Test A (CKD subjects before dialysis)

T₃ = Test B (CKD subjects after dialysis); SS = Statistically significant

DISCUSSIONS

We have compared the Mean and Standard deviations of pre-dialysis and post-dialysis with the normal (Control) in assessing renal function. There was observable significant difference in sodium parameters in which we had 146.01 ± 8.62 mmol/L for pre-dialysis, and 147.30 ± 11.45 mmol/L for post-dialysis when compared to the Normal that gave 134 ± 4.0 mmol/L with P < 0.01 and F = 6.96 as shown in table 1.

Similar observations were seen in lipid profile parameters where there were marked significant difference for control, pre-dialysis and post dialysis (see Table 2).

In the case of sodium, a potential explanation for the observed increase during the pre-haemodialysis and post-haemodialysis phases may be attributed to the disruption of sodium balance in patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD) which arise from compromised renal excretion and subsequent sodium retention. Our findings here deviate from the findings of [5], which indicated that post-dialysis patients exhibited significantly elevated sodium concentration in comparison to pre-haemodialysis pa-

tients. The authors attributed this phenomenon to the diffusion of sodium from the dialysis solution.

There was no significant difference observed in potassium, chloride and bicarbonate concentrations among the pre-haemodialysis and post-haemodialysis phases of the patients with renal failure and control group. The stability of potassium and chloride may be due to effective dialysis control, while bicarbonate levels, though slightly higher in dialysis patients did not reach statistical significance. This finding correlates with a study by [6], who observed significant decrease in potassium concentration post-dialysis compared to the pre-haemodialysis. The levels of Total Cholesterol (TC) were markedly elevated in the post dialysis phase among patients experiencing renal failure when juxtaposed with the control group. Nevertheless, no substantial differences were observed between the control group and the pre-dialysis phase, nor between the pre-dialysis and post-dialysis phase. The increase in total concentration following dialysis may be explained by haemoconcentration resulting from the removal of fluid throughout the dialysis procedure. Hypercholesterolaemia is frequently observed in individuals diagnosed with Chronic Kidney Disease

(CKD) especially those receiving dialysis treatment due to the disruption of lipid metabolism [7]. The results of this study stand in contrast to the findings reported by [8,9], who indicated that Total Cholesterol levels were elevated in post dialysis. [10], had earlier reported no notable difference.

The observed decrease in HDL levels among patients undergoing dialysis may be linked to heightened oxidative stress and modification in lipoprotein metabolism, phenomenon that are frequently encountered in chronic disease [11]. Our findings support this earlier claim and those of [12-14]. Inclusion of these profile tests could be helpful in management of renal dysfunctional state.

REFERENCES

1. Furgan A.L (2014). Evaluation of Some Chemical Changes Associated with Chronic Renal Failure Patients Undergoing Haemodialysis in al najaf governorate. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*. 4: 1-20.
2. Stern A. (2014). High Blood Pressure in Dialysis Patients: Causes, Pathophysiology, Influence on Morbidity, Mortality and Management, National Institute of Health.
3. Akchurin O, M & Kaskel F (2015). Update on Inflammation in Chronic Kidney Disease. *Blood Purification*. 39: 84-97.
4. Sarhat E, R & Mutadha N.A (2013). Biochemical Changes in Chronic Renal Failure Pre and Post Hemolysis. *Journal Environmental Science and Engineering A*. 5: 190-195.
5. Canand B, Chazot C, Koomans J & Collins A (2019). Fluid and Haemodynamic Management in Haemodialysis Patients: Challenges and Opportunities. *Journal Brasileiro de Netrologia*. 41: 550-559.
6. Correa S, Scover K.M, Tumlin J.A, Roy-Chandhury P, Koplan B.A, Costea A.I, Kher V, Williamson D, (2021). Electrolyte Changes in Contemporary Haemodialysis: A Secondary Analysis of the Monitoring in Dialysis (MID) Study. *Kidney*. 360: 695-707.
7. Bulbul MC, Dageel T, Asfar B, Ullusu NN Cuwabara M, Covic A, Kanbay B. (2018). Disorders of Lipid Metabolism in Chronic Kidney Disease. *Blood Purification*. 46: 144-152.
8. Parashar SK, Pathak S & Arora HS (2024). Changes in Lipid Profile in Chronic Kidney Disease Patients on Haemodialysis *International Journal of Medicine and Public Health*. 14: 415-419.
9. Maurya N.K, Sengar N.S, Arya P (2018). Impact on Haemodialysis on Lipid Profile Among Chronic Renal Failure Patients (Regular and Non-regular Hemodialysis). *The Pharma Innovation Journal*. 7: 363-365.
10. Sharma H, Shah T, Gorasia JH, Baria DP (2012) Lipid Profile and Lipoprotein (a) in Chronic Renal Failure Patients with and without Haemodialysis. *International Journal of Medicine and Public Health*. 2: 28-31.
11. Rysz J, Glube Brzozka A, Rysz-Gorzyrska B, Franczyk, B (2020). The Role and Function of HDL in Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease and the Risk of Cardiovascular Disease. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 21: 1-19.
12. Heidari B (2013). C-reactive Protein and Other Markers of Inflammation in Hemolysis Patients. *Caspian Journal of Internal Medicine*. 4: 611-616.
13. Al-Rubaie HA, & Hassan D.D (2014). Assessment of Haematological and Biochemical Parameters in Haemodialysis Patients and the Impact of Haemodialysis in Duration on Hepcidin, Ferritin and CRP. *Iraqi Journal of Haematology*. 3: 85-97.
14. Hanygan M, Hashim MA, & Ainashef I.M (2016). Superoxide ion: Generation and Chemical Implications. *Chemical Review*. 116: 3029-3085.

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